

ASSESSING THE EFFECT OF PUBLIC PARTICIPATION ON POLICY EFFECTIVENESS AND CITIZEN COMPLIANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF CIVIC ENGAGEMENT

*Safdar Nadeem Ch¹., Nazar Hussain¹, Muhammad Shafique¹ , Jadul¹, Abdul Jabbar²

Shah Abdul Latif University
COMSATS University Islamabad

Safdarnadeem129@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14842412>

Keywords

Public participation, Policy effectiveness, Citizen Compliance, Civic engagement

Article History

Received on 26 December 2024

Accepted on 26 January 2025

Published on 10 February 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Public participation in policy effectiveness is crucial for ensuring transparency, accountability, and responsiveness in governance. This research aims to deepen the understanding of citizen's involvement in the policy-making process to boost compliance and flourishing execution. It illustrates the principle of democracy by giving opportunity of raising a voice that directly affects their personal lives as well as community. A quantitative research approach was used, surveying 200 respondents to collect data. Findings depicted that public participation positively influences both policy effectiveness and citizen compliance. Moreover, civic engagement considerably mediates its critical role in enhancing trust and alliance between the public and policymakers. This study also highlighted importance of inclusive and effective civic engagement in enhancing policy legitimacy and strengthening democracy.

INTRODUCTION

Public participation is generally valued while electoral process in any democratic system. However, populace involvement in policy making and its compliance during execution is not given due weightage in countries like Pakistan. Citizens will have faith in their top leadership, when their essential needs are addressed through tangible policies. Public Participation while formulation of policies will

strengthen the bond between the people and Government.

Hence, it leads to good governance and helps in solving intimate social problems. Policies made after deliberate public participation are long lasting and efficiently produce desired outcomes. Moreover, populace greets the policies which are based on their genuine needs and in line with societal values for

compliance in true letter and spirit. Policy makers also call for legitimate input by think tanks and enlightened citizens as per required demography and culture to make valuable parameters for implementation of directives. Public participation is mostly done by using various techniques and approaches (Jo & Nabatchi, 2021). Likewise, Public values assessment (PVA) is a practice of identifying, reflecting and deciding on public values, performed for a given policy issue. It improves policy making procedures and results (Nabatchi, 2012). Good governance is achieved through effective citizen's participation in policy making. It is also well said that leadership makes well perceived decisions by incorporating the insights and preferences of the society (Li, 2015). Community engagement in decision-making processes can educate the public, assess public acceptance of strategies and legitimize final results (Jordan et al, 2016). Public participation is linked with those who are to be penalized by the absolute decisions. They must be given right to part of the process (iap2.org). Public participation demands the investment of special resources on the part of organizations and citizens to address the concerns of the society. Public participation demands time, energy and exposes organizations for criticism. It requires strong agreement of trust and accessibility of both citizens and administrators (Letki & Steen, 2021). Regardless of challenges like time constraints, manipulation by pressure groups and profit seekers, Public participation remains crucial in policy effectiveness. Civil society contribution brings sense of ownership and trust in the system. The level of public participation leads to credible and widely accepted policies and their successful compliance.

This paper aims to assess the effect of public participation with regards to implication of policies for good governance and sustainable policies through mediating role of civic engagement.

Research Objectives

1. To elaborate the importance of public participation in policy effectiveness.
2. To know the effects of public participation on citizens compliance.

3. To examine the mediating role of civic engagement in the relationship between public participation and policy effectiveness.
4. To assess the mediating role of civic engagement in the relationship between public participation and citizen compliance.

Research Questions

1. How does public participation impact policy effectiveness?
2. How does public participation effect citizen's compliance to the policies?
3. What is the association between public participation and policy effectiveness through mediating effect of civic engagement?
4. What is the association between public participation and citizen's compliance through mediating effect of civic engagement?

Literature Review

In 1960 Public participation and governance became an important topic for the researchers. However, Focus of interest, significance and methodology of public participation has seen many ups and downs over the time. Fifty years ago, in 1969 Sherry Arnstein wrote a master piece "The eight rungs of the Ladder of Citizen Participation" which is one of the most vastly cited and renowned in the field even today. She explained the ladder of increasing citizen's influence and ability over government policies and decision making (Boyte 1989, Polletta 2012). Many experts opine that democratic system, transparency and public participation raise the level of confidence in the public institution. Moreover, transparency is the confirmation and foundation of any government's integrity, accountability and empowerment of citizens. Transparency reduces the gap between stakeholders and brings trust in public decisions (Kimand Lee, 2017). Public participation allows community members to engage with the state during the policy formulation process. Civic engagement allows informed decisions for community development and service delivery (Buccus, Hemson, et al., 2007). Development has been viewed as a product of government involvement in the society. Understanding policymaker's observations about the suitable role of citizens in the democratic path has considerable relevance. From a

normative point of view, the role of civil society is a key aspect that distinguishes different understandings of democracy. Democracy theories (Participatory and Elitist) describe different versions on the scope of civic engagement. Elitist conceptualizes citizen's role to electing democratic leaders only but in participatory model citizen's involvement is seen more dynamically in decision making process (Held, 2006, Nylen, 2003).

Public Participation and Policy Effectiveness

Public participation is based on the belief that policy effectiveness is possible through maximum involvement of citizens in the process (iap2.org). Public participation is a vital factor for increasing policy legitimacy by bridging the gap between the government and the public. Moreover, as per Sveinung Arnesen (2017) public participation can enhance the legitimacy of policies by aligning them with society's preferences and values. Public participation in decision-making process leads to policies being perceived as fair and transparent (Boothe, 2021). Furthermore, Policies embossed by society members get more public support for government decisions (Irvin & Stansbury, 2004). Empowerment, legitimacy and learning motivate policymakers to get public participation for policy effectiveness. Legitimacy facilitates soft execution and reduces resistance from stakeholders (Tyler, 1990). Participation is the only way to empower people and thus to put in practice democratic ideals to obtain consensus from citizen's knowledge when facing complex issues (Hisschemöller & Cuppen, 2015), Thus enhancing policy effectiveness with the help of public participation.

Public Participation and Citizen Compliance

Tyler (2006) states that whenever, public is part of the policy-making process, they are more liable to abide by the policies, because they feel greater sense of responsibility and association with the decisions. Public participation during policy formulation considerably affects **citizen's compliance**, it refers to the degree to which public voluntarily adhere to laws,

rules and policies. This bond between participation and compliance is supported by numerous theoretical frameworks, which includes natural justice (**voice, neutrality**, respect and trust) social contract theory (responsibility, sharing and shared responsibility) **and** trust in government institutions (competency in services delivery and transparency). It has been emphasized by many scholars that public participation leads to more valuable and persistent compliance to the laws across various policy domains (Tyler, Frey & Stutzer, 2006). When citizens are given a voice in the policy-making process, they perceive the process as just, lawful, and transparent, for voluntarily compliance.

Civic Engagement as Mediating Factor

Civic engagement is defined as dynamic involvement of citizens in the political, social, and civic activities to enhance well-being of society. It plays a decisive role between public participation, policy effectiveness and citizen compliance. Civic engagement encompasses a broader spectrum of activities, such as community organizing, volunteer ship, social activism, and advocacy (Putnam, 2000). According to Van Holm et al. (2020), during pandemic of COVID-19 it has been observed that civic engagement played a major role in mediating trust and compliance. In the areas where, civic engagement was high, citizens were having faith in health guidelines issued by the government and same was acted upon like social distancing and mandatory wearing of masks. It indicates the importance of civic engagement to build the trust in line with the compliance of policies. Whenever, citizens are actively engaged in budgetary process, they comply with local taxation policies and contribute to community development in a best possible way (Wampler, 2012). Moreover, quality civic engagement plays its role as a catalyst for translating public participation into tangible governance effects visible to the society. Basic research model of this study is as under (Fig 1).

Hypotheses: This article is based on the following hypotheses:-

1. **H1:** Public participation has significant and positive impact on policy effectiveness.
2. **H2:** Public participation has significant and positive impact on citizen compliance.
3. **H3:** Public participation has significant and positive impact on policy effectiveness through mediating effect of civic engagement.
4. **H4:** Public participation has significant and positive impact on citizen compliance through mediating effect of civic engagement.

Research Methodology

This is a quantitative cross sectional study. Regression analysis is used to investigate the effect of independent variable Public Participation (PP) on both dependent variables, which are Policy Effectiveness (PE) and Citizen Compliance (CC) with Civic Engagement (CE) as a mediator. A cross sectional survey has been conducted to collect data from urban and rural residents of Sukkur and Hyderabad Districts of Sind Province.

Data Analysis. The study has been conducted using random sampling technique with a sample size (n) of 200 (involved in public participation activities in different policy matters). During this study, factors like age, gender, education and socioeconomic status has been given due consideration. The aim of data analysis is to assess the relationships between public participation, policy effectiveness, citizen compliance, and mediating role of civic engagement.

Frequency Distribution.

The purpose of frequency distribution is to provide a summary of the respondent’s information i.e gender, age and education. Frequency distribution provides percentage of the demographic factors of the respondents. Following table indicates details frequency distribution and in this study maximum participation is by male graduates of age between 25 -35 Yrs. Frequency distribution statistical table is as under:-

Factors	Category	Frequency (n = 200)	Percentage
Gender	Male	140	70%
	Female	60	30%
Age	20-25 Yrs	62	31%
	26-35 Yrs	92	46%
	36-45 Yrs & above	46	23%
Education	Intermediate	36	18%
	Graduation & Equivalent	98	49%
	Masters/ PhD & above	66	33%

Reliability Test

Cronbach Alpha (α) measures statistically reliability of responded items. Its value ranges between 0 to 1.

Moreover, value 0.7 and above shows acceptable reliability.

Variables	No of Questions/ items	Cronbach Alpha (α)Values	Remarks
Public Participation	5	0.8	Good
Policy Effectiveness	5	0.8	Good
Citizen Compliance	5	0.7	Acceptable
Civic Engagement	5	0.8	Good

Correlation Matrix

In this study, the value of Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) is calculated for assessing the relationships between public participation (independent variable), policy effectiveness (dependent variable), citizen compliance

(dependent variable) and civic engagement (mediating factor). The value of coefficient (r) ranges from -1 to +1 (+1 shows positive correlation and -1 shows negative correlation). Statistical table with values of Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) is as under.

Variables	PP	PE	CC	CE	Remarks
Public Participation (PP)	1				Significant & Positive
Policy Effectiveness (PE)	0.64	1			"
Citizen Compliance (CC)	0.59	0.61	1		"
Civic Engagement (CE)	0.67	0.62	0.59	1	"

Regression Analysis Statistical Table

A hierarchical regression analysis has been used to test the relationships between variables and the mediating role of civic engagement. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS. Moreover, The

Baron and Kenny method was used to test the mediating role of citizen’s compliance. Statistical data is as under:-

Serial	Relationships of variables	Un standardized Coefficient (B)	Standard Error (SE)	Standardized Coefficient (β)	t value	p-value	R ²
a.	Public Participation and Policy effectiveness	0.484	0.064	0.553	7.805	< 0.001	0.30
b.	Public Participation and citizen compliance	0.446	0.057	0.527	7.056	< 0.001	0.27
c.	Mediating effect of Civic engagement on Policy effectiveness	0.407	0.059	0.509	8.071	< 0.001	0.45
d.	Mediating effect of Civic engagement on citizen compliance	0.354	0.042	0.426	7.856	< 0.001	0.40

Results and Discussions

a. The relationship between Public Participation and Policy Effectiveness shows a significant and positive impact [B = 0.484, β = 0.553, $p < 0.001$]. This means that increased public participation leads to greater perception of policy effectiveness, indicating 30% [R² = 0.30] of the variance.

b. The relationship between Public Participation and citizen compliance shows a significant and positive impact [B = 0.446, β = 0.527, $p < 0.001$]. It depicts that public participation augments citizen compliance, indicating 27% [R² = 0.27] of the variance.

c. The mediating factor **civic engagement** has a significant and positive effect on policy effectiveness [B = 0.407, β = 0.509, $p < 0.001$] with value of variance of 45% [R² = 0.45].

The mediating factor civic engagement shows significant and positive effect [B = 0.354, β = 0.426, $p < 0.001$], indicating 40% [R² = 0.40] of the variance in citizen compliance.

Conclusion

It is concluded from above analyzed results that public participation has major impact on policy effectiveness and its legitimacy. The study highlights that public support, acceptance of policy decisions, compliance with policies, trust in government institutions, policy effectiveness, as well as transparency and accountability in policy making processes can be achieved by halfway meeting of citizens and the government. The research has also concluded that government must take initiatives to engage public for community development and to address the rising sentiments. Public participation and citizen’s compliance to policies are interconnected, thereby asking policymakers to design a comprehensive way out for valuable participation mechanism. It is evident and acknowledged from the study that critical role of public participation, governments and its institutions can enhance public trust and achieve accomplishment in implementing more sustainable and effective policies. The author has emphasized the importance of public participation by two way communication for policy legitimacy, strengthening democracy and ensuring more responsive policies aligned with the needs and values of society.

REFERENCES

Jo, S., & Nabatchi, T. (2020). Different Processes, Different Outcomes? Assessing the Individual-Level Impacts of Public Participation. *Public Administration Review* Volume 81, Issue 1 Pages 137-15. doi:10.1111/puar.13272.

Arnstein, S. R. (1969). A ladder of citizen participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), 216-224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>.

Peterlin, J, Pearse, N & Dimovski, V. (2015). Strategic Decision Making for Organizational Sustainability: The Implications of Servant Leadership and Sustainable Leadership Approaches. *Economic and Business Review*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.15458/85451.4>.

Jordan, M., et al (2016). What citizens want to know about their government’s finances: Closing

the information gap. *The Social Science Journal*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2016.04.007>.

Letki & Steen, (2021). Social-Psychological Context Moderates Incentives to Co-produce: Evidence from a Large-Scale Survey Experiment on Park Upkeep in an Urban Setting. *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 81, Issue 5, 935-950. doi: 10.1111/puar.13340.

Polletta, Francesca, and Pang Ching Bobby Chen, (2012) Narrative and Social Movements, *The Oxford Handbook of Cultural Sociology*, Oxford Handbooks , <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195377767.013.18>.

Boyte, Harry C, (1989). Politics as education, *Social Policy*, 1990, Vol 20, Issue 4, p35

Tae Ho Lee and Lois A. Boynton, (2017) Conceptualizing transparency: Propositions for the integration of situational factors and stakeholder’s perspectives. *Public Relations Inquiry* 2017, Vol. 6(3) 233-251.

Buccus, Hemson, et al., (2007). Community development and engagement with local governance in South Africa **Community Development Journal**, Volume 43, Issue 3, July 2008, Pages 297-311, <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsn011>.

Letki & Steen, (2021). Social-Psychological Context Moderates Incentives to Co-produce: Evidence from a Large-Scale Survey Experiment on Park Upkeep in an Urban Setting, *Public Administration Review* Volume 81, Issue 5 p. 935-950. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13340>

Nylen, W.R. (2003). Conclusion In: *Participatory Democracy versus Elitist Democracy: Lessons from Brazil*. Palgrave Macmillan, New York. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781403980304_9

Boothe, K. (2021). (Re) defining legitimacy in Canadian drug assessment policy? Comparing ideas over time. *Health Economics, Policy and Law*, 16(4), 424-439.

- Arnesen, S., & Peters, Y. (2018). The legitimacy of representation: How descriptive, formal, and responsiveness representation affect the acceptability of political decisions. *Comparative Political Studies*, 51(7), 868-899.
- Irvin, R. A., & Stansbury, J. (2004). Citizen participation in decision making: is it worth the effort?. *Public administration review*, 64(1), 55-65.
- Hisschemöller, M., & Cuppen, E. (2015). Participatory assessment: tools for empowering, learning and legitimating?. In *The tools of policy formulation* (pp. 33-51). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Stutzer, A., & Frey, B. S. (2006). Political participation and procedural utility: An empirical study. *European Journal of Political Research*, 45(3), 391-418.
- Holmes, E. A., O'Connor, R. C., Perry, V. H., Tracey, I., Wessely, S., Arseneault, L & Bullmore, E. (2020). Multidisciplinary research priorities for the COVID-19 pandemic: a call for action for mental health science. *The lancet psychiatry*, 7(6), 547-560.
- Hisschemöller, M., & Cuppen, E. (2015). Participatory assessment: tools for empowering, learning and legitimating?. In *The tools of policy formulation* (pp. 33-51). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Wampler, B. (2012). Participatory budgeting: Core principles and key impacts. *Journal of Public Deliberation*.
- Putnam, R. D. (2000). Bowling alone: America's declining social capital. In *Culture and politics: A reader* (pp. 223-234). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Kelleher, C., & Lowery, D. (2009). Central city size, metropolitan institutions and political participation: Contextual influences on the political behavior of the Latino population. *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 31(2), 123-143. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9906.2008.00498.x>
- Leach, W. D. (2006). Collaborative public management and democracy: Evidence from western watershed partnerships. *Public Administration Review*, 66(S1), 100-110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2006.00670.x>
- OECD. (2001). *Citizens as partners: Information, consultation and public participation in policy-making*. OECD Publishing.
- Petunia, T.A. & Selepe, M., (2020), 'Strengthening policy and decision-making processes through community participation: A municipal perspective', *Africa's Public Service Delivery and Performance Review* 8(1), a409. <https://doi.org/10.4102/apsdpr.v8i1.409>
- Abelson, J., & Gauvin, F. P. (2006). *Assessing the impacts of public participation: Concepts, evidence and policy implications*. Ottawa: Canadian Policy Research Networks
- Thelma, C. C. (2024). Civic education and citizen participation in local governance: A case of Lusaka District, Zambia. *Journal homepage: www.ijrpr.com* ISSN, 2582, 7421.